

EMPOWERING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS THROUGH PROJECT-BASED LEARNING

Mutalova Mokhinur Tolibjon kizi

Teacher of Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

mokhinur9925@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11632862>

Abstract: In this thesis, the main specific purpose and effectiveness of teaching languages based on the project method, the formation of oneself and one's own capabilities in the process of studying based on the project method, the development of research skills, the project method in teaching practice and about the educational project.

Key words: foreign languages, project method, education, problem situation, analysis, understanding of problems, project task.

Introduction:

Design-based training solves certain tasks of education: to help the growth of personal confidence, self-realization and reflection of each participant who is trained on the basis of the project. By feeling the "achievement situation" in the lesson (*or outside of the lesson*) not in words, but in practice, the student learns that he is needed, lucky and has the ability to overcome various problematic situations.

The student feels himself and his capabilities in the process of studying based on the project method. While working together in a team, they realize their contribution, and in the process of completing the project task, they gain new knowledge and skills, while completing the project, students develop an understanding of the importance of working as a team to achieve results. Student's cooperative activities in the process of performing creative tasks, inspiring the development of communicative qualities in them, own approach to solving problems, the ability to have a small point of view and at the same time to be able to listen to others, sometimes Develops the ability to listen to others who are completely opposite to his opinion. The method of projects plays an important role in the development of students' ability to observe and think.

It is aimed to develop the following skills in the student through the project method:

Development of research skills;

- analyzing the problematic situation, understanding the problems, extracting the necessary information from sources and literature and using them;

- organization of observation of practical situations, determination and analysis of their results;

- building hypotheses, carrying out their verification, summarizing, drawing conclusions.

The specified goals individually organize the breadth of education and affect the qualities of a person. The student has a process of personal growth for change. It forms the ability to realize the concept of the word "I", to learn and explore the world, and to master the means of thinking.

When the project method is used in the teaching practice, the student develops various abilities, while in the traditional teaching, "knowledge" is given. In traditional education, the descriptive-explanatory method of teaching is the priority in imparting knowledge to the student. The educational process is fully controlled by this method, students are monitored, and the subject is asked in a reproductive form. The main goal of this approach is the formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications, and the reimagining of the leading view of the activity. The project method is focused on the person being trained. One of the indicators of personality development is students' mastery of observation skills (synthesis, comparison, generalization, categorization, induction, deduction, abstraction, etc.). The most important thing is that the student needs to develop his personality, to change himself, to develop the emotional and image sphere, and to acquire the skills of emotional value relationships. Project-based teaching in this way is an effective alternative to the classroom-lesson system. But it cannot completely replace the traditional norm. Because the world education system has accumulated a golden reserve of pedagogical methods, approaches, and technologies for a hundred years. According to experts, the project method is used as an addition to other forms of education, and it turns out to be an acceleration of personal growth.

From the point of view of the educational project or research teacher, this is an integrative didactic tool of development, teaching and upbringing. It allows the emergence and development of unique educational skills of design and research in the student. *A learning project or research will teach students exactly the following:*

- to review the breadth of problem solving problems and to separate the problems under the problems, to set the leading problems and tasks arising from these problems.

- formation and planning of the student's meaningful activity;

- analysis and reflection of one's own activity (*result of solving the problems of the project and its success*);

- to show the results of one's activity and the progress of the work;

The project should be scientifically understood, summarized, classified and the scope of its effective application should be defined. The strong development of innovations in pedagogy makes it possible to widely use the design method, and it becomes necessary with the classification of educational projects, their methodical execution, the introduction of educational projects into the educational system, and the formation of new courses. Educational projects occupy a leading place in education at the school. Different fields of knowledge are involved for such purposes of knowledge. Projects are categorized by different levels. For example, according to the subject areas, according to the volume of activity, according to the implementation, according to the number of performers, according to the importance of the results. Depending on the type of projects, all of them will have a unique authorship feature, which will be unique. All projects are aimed at achieving some goal. At the same time, there will be temporary restrictions. Educational projects are different. Projects ranging from one lesson to one year. There will be individual, group and school-wide projects for different ages.

The results of the project may be different according to its form. For example, video film, multimedia, presentation, performance, bills, games, etc. Time projects are divided into mini-projects. They occupy a lesson or part of a lesson. Short-term projects are carried out during 2-6 lessons. In medium-term projects, 12-15 lessons are spent in extracurricular and in-class activities, as well as in long-term projects. Also, the full cycle is performed outside of class. By completing the project, the student will use his strength, his knowledge, make a profit, and show the result he has achieved in front of many people. This is an activity aimed at solving an interesting problem, often formed by students themselves in the form of a task. The result of this activity is the found method of solving the problem - it has a practical nature. It has important practical importance and is interesting and important for the discoverers themselves.

References:

1. Akhmedova S. R. Effectiveness of integration of educational processes
2. Science and education. - 2021. - Volume 2. -N.: 9. - S. 369-373.
3. English language teaching methodology: textbook for pedagogical institutes and pedagogical universities.
4. Faculties of foreign languages. - L.: Education, 1975. - 312 p.
5. Rogova G.V. Methodology of teaching English

